

Stress Management Strategies and Social Studies Teacher Classroom Effectiveness in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

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ABSTRACT: The study investigated the relationship between stress management strategies and classroom effectiveness among Social Studies teachers in upper basic schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted the correlation design. A sample size of one hundred Social Studies teachers was used for the study. The instrument for the data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Stress Management Strategies and Social Studies Teachers Classroom Effectiveness Questionnaire (SMSSSTCREQ). A Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistic was used for estimating the consistency of the instrument, this yielded a reliability index of 0.07, indicating a high reliability. Data were analysed using coefficient of determination to answer the research questions, while the linear regression statistics was used to test the stated null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings show a significant relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness, a significant relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness, no significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness. It was recommended that teachers should find their optimal stress level and effectively manage it by adopting effective stress management strategies, teachers should adopt the stress management of taking regular breaks to boost their classroom teaching effectiveness, teachers should be encouraged to maintain a healthy lifestyle so as to be productive at any point in time.

INTRODUCTION

Education serves as a conduit for the dissemination of knowledge, skills, and character traits, manifesting in a variety of forms (Obro, Ogheneakoke & Odesa, 2023). Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world. The influence of education transcends mere skill acquisition necessary for economic prosperity; it plays a vital role in fostering nation-building and facilitating reconciliation (Obro & Nwalado, 2020). Teachers are usually faced with lots of stressors because of the scope. The scope of Social Studies is vast encompassing the study of human society from various angles. This subject is fundamental in equipping students with the knowledge necessary to comprehend their environment and their role within it, thereby preparing them for future challenges.

Teachers can be leaders, knowledge workers, facilitators, supervisors, mentors, scaffolders, social engineers, and reflective practitioners (Sahla, 2019, Atakpo, 2020a). Teachers assume leadership roles such as instructional specialist and change agent. They are critical thinkers in their field since they are knowledge workers. As facilitators, they support self-directed learning while preserving a healthy balance between freedom and guidance. Additional responsibilities include student supervision, mentoring new teachers, supporting learning, interacting with students, and promoting self-reflection as a means of continuous improvement (Atakpo, 2020b). The nature of a teacher’s work requires them to prepare daily for the educational process, including the daily preparation of lessons, and to support them through educational means and various teaching methods.

Stress and anxiety can affect teachers’ effectiveness in the classroom. In a study by Anxiety and Depression Association of American (2019) 56 % of teachers reported that anxiety and stress affected their work performance. Due to stress in the work place, constant worry or concern about one's performance can be overwhelming and lead to less productive work days. Stress can make it difficult to focus and engage in daily work. The biggest threat to productivity and classroom effectiveness is not just stress but how stress management into more significant well-being issues that impact teachers’ performance. Knowing the effects of stress on productivity is critical to organizations commitment to higher performing employees and retention.

Stress management is the process of identifying, understandings and taking action to manage stress and increase well-being. It includes activities such as analyzing stressors and learning to recognize signs of stress, developing coping strategies and setting and achieving goals (Ogbeide & Enabunene, 2023). Stress management strategies is very important because it helps teachers learn how

to reduce the physical and emotional symptoms of stress, improve overall life satisfaction and also help in effective teaching and learning.

One of most demanding profession is the teaching profession and teachers are often faced with stress levels due to increasing workloads, low salaries and lack of support from administration, managing descriptive behaviours and balancing personal and professional responsibilities. As such it is essential to assess the stress management strategies skills of teachers to determine the impact on their performance and effectiveness (Adeyemi, 2016).

The impact of not adopting the right stress management strategies on stress from workload, long hours at work and work intensification was found to have a major and everlasting effect on organizations, as employees were learner experiencing more stress and uncertainty because companies got without building muscle (Niyi & Ejimonye, 2023). Hartney (2016) in his study on stress management to enhance teachers' quality, stress is a well-established concept in the psychological literature, and teaching in particular is recognized as a highly stressful profession. Hartney (2016) Grouped teachers' stressors into four major categories: Individual teachers stressors, student related stressors, Team related stressors and Role related stressors.

Marwa et al. (2018) conducted a study on stress and coping mechanisms employed by teachers in general education and special education classrooms. Given the variety of duties teachers have, including classroom management, lesson planning, preparation, student evaluation, and resource management, teaching is seen as a difficult career. Particularly when working with students who have learning disabilities, teachers serve as the main point of contact for parents, other students, and faculty members. Teachers can employ a variety of coping mechanisms to manage stress at school. Since stressors cannot be eliminated from the classroom. Manal (2020) in her study on work stress related problems in the teachers of Social Studies in government schools in Qatar affirmed that work stress is experienced by Social Studies teachers in Qatar and that it can be both physiological and psychological sources of stress that often get multiplied by students' behaviour and teachers' inability to cope with stress. Among other factors that can increase the stress are teachers' relationship with his colleagues, the ambiguity of his professional role, the burden of work and the absence of understanding between the teacher and the school administration, and that such stress that teacher physical and emotional resources are depleted as a result of the stress they endure in their work (Akpotu, Atakpo & Obed-Chukwuka, 2024). It is on this basis that the study investigated stress management strategies and Social Studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State

RQs

1. What is the relationship between Stress management of taking regular breaks during the day and Social Studies teachers class room effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between Stress management of Maintaining a healthy life style and Social Studies teachers class room effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between stress management of eating balanced diet and Social Studies teachers class room effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and social studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and social studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and social studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

METHODS

The study adopted the correlation research design. The aim of using this design is to examine the relationship between stress management strategies and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The population of the study consisted of 605 Social Studies teachers from the post primary Education boarding in the 25 local Government Area of Delta State. The study sample comprised of 100 teachers and the simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample size. The study instrument was a structured questionnaire titled "Stress Management Strategies and Social Studies Teachers Classroom Effectiveness Questionnaire (SMSSTCREQ). The questionnaire was section A and B. Section A consisted of the demographic information, while Section B contained fifteen (15) items on stress management strategies. A 4-point rating scale of Strongly Disagree (SD) 1, Disagree (D) 2, Agreed (A) 3, and Strongly Agree (SA) 4.

To ascertain the reliability of the instrument the researcher used the test-retest reliability method was utilised. Using Person's product moment correlation statistics in SPSS and a Coefficient of 0.70 was obtained signifying that the instrument is reliable. The Data obtained from the study were analysed using coefficient of determination to answer the research questions, while the linear regression statistics was used to test the stated null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Results collected data are presented in the tables based on research questions

RQ1: What is the relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks during the day relate to social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Coefficient of Determination Analysis of Stress Management of Taking Regular Breaks During the Day and Social Studies Teachers Classroom Effectiveness.

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Stress management of taking regular breaks	100	0.256	0.066	6.6%	Positive relationship
Classroom Effectiveness	100				

Table 1, showed that $r = 0.256$ is the extent of the relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks during the day relate to Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The coefficient of determination is 0.066 and the amount of contribution stress management of taking regular breaks during the day made towards students’ classroom effectiveness is 6.6%. However, the result showed a positive relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks during the day and Social Studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

RQ2: What is the relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle relate to social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Coefficient of Determination Analysis of Stress Management of Maintaining a Healthy Lifestyle and Social Studies Teachers Classroom Effectiveness.

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle	100	0.267	0.071	7.1%	Positive relationship
Classroom Effectiveness	100				

Table 2, indicated that $r = 0.267$ and this is the extent of relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The coefficient of determination is 0.071 and the amount of contribution stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle made towards social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness is 7.1%. Hence, the result showed a positive high extent relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

RQ3: What is the relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets relate to social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination Analysis on Stress Management of Eating Balanced Diets and Social Studies Teachers Classroom Effectiveness.

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Stress Management of Eating Balanced Diets	100	0.123	0.015	1.5	Low/Positive relationship
Classroom Effectiveness	100				

Table 3 showed that $r = 0.123$ and is the extent of relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The coefficient of determination is 0.015 and the amount of contribution stress management of eating balanced diets made towards social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State is 1.5%. The result showed a low positive relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and social studies teachers’ classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho: There is no significant relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Linear Regression Analysis on stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	9.937	1	9.937	6.888	.010
Residual	141.373	98	1.443		
Total	151.310	99			

Coefficient					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.772	.621		28.639	.000
Stress Management of Regular Breaks	.104	.040	.256	2.625	.010

The result in table 4, shows the regression output which shows a linear relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The computed $F(1, 98) = 6.888$ $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and Social Studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 5: Linear Regression Analysis on stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and Social Studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Anova					
	Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	10.769	1	10.769	7.509	.007 ^b
Residual	140.541	98	1.434		
Total	151.310	99			

Coefficient					
	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant)	21.556	.807		26.726	.000
Stress Management of healthy lifestyle	-.142	.052	-.267	-2.740	.007

Table 5, indicates the regression output which shows a linear relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and social studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The computed $F(1, 98) = 7.509$, $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 4.11: Linear Regression Analysis on stress management of eating balanced diets and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Anova					
	Sum of Square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	2.288	1	2.288	1.505	.223
Residual	149.022	98	1.521		
Total	151.310	99			

Coefficient	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant)	18.277	.899		20.320	.000
Stress Management of Eating Balanced Diets	.062	.050	.123	1.227	.223

P ≤ 0.05 level of significance; N = 100

In table 11, the regression output shows a linear relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The computed $F(1, 98) = 1.505, p < 0.05$. However, the null hypothesis was accepted. This revealed that there was no significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and social studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State.

DISCUSSION

The result of hypothesis one reveals that there is significant relationship between stress management of taking regular breaks and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. This finding submits that stress management of taking regular breaks influences Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. Engaging in regular intervals of respite, including micro breaks, lunch breaks, and extended pauses, fosters a beneficial correlation with overall well-being and productivity. By incorporating these intervals, an individual's performance can be enhanced. This practice serves to mitigate or avert stress, aids in sustaining performance throughout the day, and diminishes the necessity for prolonged recuperation at day's end. This finding agrees with Kim and Gong (2017), Lyubykh and Gulseren (2023), Jacob (2023), and Fredrick and Israel (2023), who found that taking lunch breaks and detaching from work, increases level of energy at work, decreased exhaustion and improve teachers classroom effectiveness.

The result of hypotheis two shows that there was a significant relationship between stress management of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The implication of this finding is that the ability of teachers to control their behaviours that may affect their health will help them to reduce stress and maintain good health, which will in turn lead to effective classroom effectiveness. This finding suggests that healthy lifestyle increases teaching effectiveness through reduction and absence of exhaustion, diseases, ill health and improving of the level of well-being throughout life. This finding is in line with Amaefule (2023) and Niyi and Ejimonye (2023), who found that maintaining a healthy life style reducing stress and boost teachers' classroom effectiveness. Maintaining a healthy life style no doubt would have helped teachers perform better in school. This is because it helps reduce or eradicate those factors that act as impediment to effective teaching.

Result of hypothesis three indicates that there was no significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. The possible reason could be that eating a balanced diet or meal may not necessarily reduce stress or exhaustion, if the individual fail to take regular breaks and maintain a healthy life style, and thus, may cumulate to teachers classroom effectiveness. Hence, no relationship was found for stress management of eating balanced diets. The finding contradicts the studies of Kadar (2014), who reported significant relationship between stress management of eating balanced diets and classroom effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it estblished that stress management of taking regular breaks, maintaining a healthy lifestyle, stress management of getting enough sleep at night, stress management of time management, stress management of social support, and stress management of peaceful working environment, all influence Social Studies teachers classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. On the other hand, the study concluded that stress management of eating balanced diets, have no impact on Social Studies teachers' classroom effectiveness in upper basic schools in Delta State. In the present study it shows that the Social Studies teachers who are able to manage their stress in a better way or have the ability to keep stress under control can move their teaching learning process effectively more than the teachers who are unable to manage their stress.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1 Teachers should find their optimal stress level and effectively manage it by adopting effective stress management strategies.
- 2 Teachers should adopt the stress management of taking regular breaks to boost their classroom teaching effectiveness
- 3 Teachers should be encouraged to maintain a healthy lifestyle so as to be productive at any point in time.,

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